

Slavic Reflexive Impersonals: Passivisation and Unaccusativity

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Background. In relation to external argumenthood, reflexive impersonal constructions show a two-way split in Slavic. In Slovenian and Polish, the constructions are active-like syntactically, which means that they generate a thematic null pronoun corresponding to the event Initiator in Spec, VoiceP (Alexiadou, Anagnostopoulou, and Schäfer 2015; Schäfer 2017). In these languages, the syntactic presence of this null pronoun is diagnosed by the admissibility of the anaphor *svoj* and the blocking of oblique agent phrases (Fehrmann et al. 2010; Rivero and Milojević Sheppard 2003; Szucsich 2008), as shown by the Slovenian example in (1a). By contrast, the Ukrainian construction is passive-like syntactically; that is, without a thematic external argument (Fehrmann et al. 2010), which is why it disallows reflexive anaphors in object position and admits the oblique realisation of the external argument (1b).

- (1) a. Bralo se je (svojo) knjigo (*od študentov). [Slovenian]
read.N REFL is own book.ACC by students
“Someone was reading (their own) book.”
- b. (Matir”ju) myjet’-sja (*svoju) dytnu. [Ukrainian]
mother.INS wash.3SG-REFL own child.ACC
“The child is being washed (by the mother).”
(Fehrmann et al. 2010, p. 206)

Passivised predicates. There is another sort of variation tied to argumenthood among Slavic impersonal constructions; namely, reflexive impersonals in Slovenian as well as Ukrainian are incompatible with passivised predicates (2a)–(2b), but this is not the case of the Polish construction, where passivisation can feed reflexive impersonalisation (2c). In the major analyses of Slavic impersonals (e.g., Fehrmann et al. 2010; Krzek 2014; Legate 2014; Rivero and Milojević Sheppard 2003), this variation is not formally accounted for, though some authors do acknowledge it (e.g., Rivero and Milojević Sheppard 2003).

- (2) a. *Bilo se je poklicano (od župana). [Slovenian]
be.PAST.N REFL is call.PASS.N by mayor
Intended: “Someone was called (by the mayor).”
- b. *Bulo pokarano-sja (druzjamy). [Ukrainian]
be.PAST.N punish.PASS.IMP-REFL friends.INS
Intended: “People were punished (by friends).”
(Anna Kryvenko, p.c.)
- c. Bywa się karanym przez przyjaciół. [Polish]
be.3SG REFL punished by friends
“From time to time people are punished by friends.”
(Rivero and Milojević Sheppard 2003, p. 112)

Proposal. In the spirit of Ruda’s (2014) and Lavine’s (2017) analyses of the related Polish *-no/-to* construction, I propose that the data in (2) can be accounted for if the reflexive is analysed as a Voice head in Slovenian and Ukrainian (but not in Polish). In fact, I propose that in both Slovenian and Ukrainian, the reflexive has the same syntactic and semantic characteristics. Semantically, it introduces the Initiator relation (3a). Syntactically, it has a c-selectional requirement due to which an NP needs to be merged in Spec, VoiceP (Bruening 2021; Schäfer 2017; Wood 2015), making it an active Voice head. Following Bruening (2013, 2021), I implement c-selection using the notation in (3b), according to which an active Voice head merges first with a VP and then its intermediate projection merges with an NP, thereby filling Spec, VoiceP. The

VoiceP of both the Ukrainian and Slovenian constructions thus shows the derivation in (3c).

- (3) a. $\llbracket se/-sja \rrbracket^g = \lambda f_{\langle s,t \rangle} \lambda x_{\langle e \rangle} \lambda e_{\langle s \rangle} [\text{Initiator}(e,x) \wedge f(e)]$
 b. *se/-sja* c-selection: [S: V, S: N]
 c. $[\text{VoiceP } pro_{\text{IMP}} [\text{Voice}' se/-sja [\text{VP V NP}_{\text{ACC}}]]]$

The only difference between the two languages lies in the semantic content of the null argument pro_{IMP} in Spec, VoiceP. In Slovenian, pro_{IMP} is an existential quantifier over humans (Rivero and Milojević Sheppard 2003) which closes the x variable of the Initiator relation introduced by *se* (3a), while in Ukrainian it is an expletive that semantically corresponds to an identity function (Schäfer 2017). Consequently, the open Initiator variable in the Ukrainian construction can be saturated by an adjunct like the NP_{INS} *Matir''ju* in (1b). Lastly, I assume syntactic dependent case (Levin and Preminger 2015), whereby case is determined configurationally rather than through the mediation of a functional head, which means that internal arguments like *knjigo* in (1a) and *dytynu* in (1b) get accusative case under c-command by pro_{IMP} in Spec, VoiceP.

Since the reflexive is a Voice head in Slovenian and Ukrainian, the ungrammaticality of (2a) and (2b) is straightforwardly accounted for – i.e., *se/-sja* stands in complementary distribution with a passive Voice head, which in contrast to (3b) syntactically does not select for an external argument NP. The Polish construction, however, can combine with passive Voice (2c). Following Legate et al. (2020), I propose that *się* in Polish is not a Voice head but rather the head of an Imp(ersonal) Phrase that immediately dominates VoiceP; syntactically, *się* has the c-selectional requirement in (4a), which states that *się* needs to merge with VoiceP rather than VP. Crucially, it does not matter for *się* what kind of VoiceP it is syntax-wise (i.e., an active one with a filled Spec or a passive one with an unfilled Spec), just so long as it combines with such a phrase. This is why reflexive impersonalisation in Polish is compatible both with active and passive verbal structures. Example (2c) thus undergoes the derivation in (4b), where pro_{IMP} (semantically again a quantifier over humans like in Slovenian) is merged within VP and there closes the Patient variable introduced by V, while the Initiator variable introduced by Voice_{PASS} is saturated by the PP in VoiceP.

- (4) a. Polish *się* c-selection: [S: VOICE]
 b. $[\text{ImpP } się [\text{VoiceP } [\text{Voice}' \text{Voice}_{\text{PASS}} [\text{VP V } pro_{\text{IMP}}]]] [\text{PP } \textit{przez przyjaciół}]]$

Lastly, I claim that the incompatibility of unaccusative predicates with impersonal reflexive constructions in Slovenian and Ukrainian (Fehrmann et al. 2010) is evidence for the present proposal that the reflexive in the two languages heads VoiceP (3c). The examples in (5) show this incompatibility for the Ukrainian construction.

- (5) a. *Včora vmerlo-sja. [Ukrainian]
yesterday died.PFV.N-REFL
 Intended: “Yesterday, someone or some people died.” (Anna Kryvenko, p.c.)
 b. *U mynulomu vmyralo-sja vid čumy.
in past died.IPFV.N-REFL from plague
 Intended: “In the past, people died from the plague.” (Anna Kryvenko, p.c.)

Assume, as is standard (Bruening 2019; Perlmutter 1978), that unaccusatives merge their sole argument within VP. However, the null impersonal pro_{IMP} in Ukrainian is an expletive, so it does not close the unaccusative V’s Patient variable; consequently, VP semantically remains of type $\langle e, st \rangle$ and therefore cannot combine with *-sja*, as the latter requires – as per (3a) – that its first semantic argument be of type $\langle s, t \rangle$. In Slovenian, the ban on unaccusatives is less strict (Ilc and Marvin 2016), as existentially interpreted sentences like (5a) are ungrammatical, but generically interpreted sentences like (5b) are allowed. In the case of existential unaccusatives, impersonal VP in Slovenian is of type $\langle s, t \rangle$, as its Patient variable is quantified over by the existentially interpreted pro_{IMP} . Such an unaccusative VP can therefore semantically combine with *se*. This combination, however, introduces the Initiator relation (see 3a), which incurs a thematic-role

violation, as an inherently one-place unaccusative predicate is turned into a two-place one. Lastly, for the generic impersonal unaccusatives in Slovenian, which are licit in contrast to the existentials, I will claim that *se* is reinterpreted through the so-called generic rescue mechanism (Härtl 2012) so that the Initiator relation is dispensed with and no thematic violation arises.

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